

P. Survey 61: Rules of a Priestly Association

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Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religions, Egyptian Religions, Text, Ancient Egyptian Religion, Ancient Egyptian Text, Funerary Beliefs and Rituals, Religious Holidays, Ancient Egyptian Religions, Language, Afro-Asiatic, Egyptian, Egyptian (Ancient), Demotic Egyptian

This papyrus contains the rules of a priestly association of mortuary priests from Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor). These mortuary priests called "choachytai" were responsible for pouring the libations for the deceased buried in the Theban necropolis on a weekly basis (Decade Festival) as well as during all major festivals celebrated in Thebes. During these so-called drinking days the choachytai did not only pour the libations for the deceased but also drank themselves in honor of the gods. Not following the rules resulted in the payment of a fine to the temple cash register.

Date Range: 109 BCE - 106 BCE

Region: Thebes (area)

Region tags: Luxor, Egypt, Africa, Thebes

Thebes is an ancient Egyptian city in Upper Egypt. The founding date is unknown, it is historically documented since the 11th dynasty. During the Middle Kingdom it became the capital of Egypt. Since the New Kingdom, the name "Waset" is documented, otherwise also Niut or Niut-reset. From the Greeks of the Ptolemaic period the name "Thēbai" (Thebes) has been preserved, but also the name "Diōs Pólis Megálē" (Great City of Zeus), from which in the time of the Roman Empire the names "Thebae" and "Diospolis Magna" were derived. Since at least the New Kingdom, the territory of Thebes included both sides of the Nile: Thebes-East and Thebes-West. Among the most important ancient sites in Thebes-West are the Valley of the Kings and the Valley of the Queens, Medinet Habu with the great temple of Ramses III, Deir el-Bahari with the mortuary temples of Hatshepsut and Mentuhotep II, as well as the Ramesseum. Thebes-East comprises the temples of Luxor and Karnak.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: F. de Cenival, *Les associations religieuses en Égypte d'après les documents démotiques*, 2 vols, Bibliothèque d'étude 46, Cairo, 1972.

– Source 2: P. W. Pestman, *The Archive of the Theban Choachytes (second century BC). A Survey of the Demotic and Greek Papyri Contained in the Archive*, *Studia Demotica* 2, Leuven, 1993

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/text/3058>
- Source 1 Description: This website contains metadata about the papyrus.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/archive/50>
- Source 2 Description: This website contains metadata about the archive in which the papyrus was kept.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.smb.museum/en/museums-institutions/aegyptisches-museum-und-papyrussammlung/home/>
- Source 1 Description: Website of the collection in which the papyrus is kept.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The papyrus was not modified.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The text was not modified.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– Yes

Notes: The papyrus was part of an archive kept in a jar in one of the tombs of the Theban necropolis. The exact circumstances of its discovery are unknown.

↳ Cemetery

– Yes

Notes: The papyrus was part of an archive kept in a jar in one of the tombs of the Theban necropolis. The exact circumstances of its discovery are unknown.

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

Notes: Many of the papyri in the archive relate to the professional activities of the mortuary priests who worked in the Theban necropolis. However, only a few texts related to the sale of their houses or were marriage contracts, which were probably first kept in a domestic context before being placed in a jar in one of the tombs where the priests worked.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: The papyrus was kept in an archive of a family of mortuary priests.

↳ Specify

– Specify: The papyrus was kept in an archive in a jar in a tomb, probably near Theban tomb 157 at Dra Abu al-Naga in the Theban necropolis.

Is the location where the text is stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The text was produced by the members of the association of Theban mortuary priests.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text was probably considered official by the members of the association. If they did not follow the rules set out in the text, they were fined. The rules were enforced by the members of the association themselves, not by a general religious body.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text was written in Demotic Egyptian, which was considered to be the script of the people, rather than a religious or sacred script, which would have been Hieratic and especially Hieroglyphic.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know exactly how many members were in the association, but presumably they were all considered to be the audience of the text, as they were all obliged to follow the rules. This included both men and women.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The religious group of mortuary priests did not actively recruit new members. The members all belonged to families of mortuary priests, a profession that had been passed down through generations. Individuals were initiated at the age of 10 and became full members at the age of 16.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: While the mortuary priests probably recited rituals when offering libations to the deceased in the necropolis, the papyrus containing the rules of their association was not used in ritual practice. Rather, it served the practical purpose of clearly defining what was allowed and the fine to be paid if the rules were broken.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The papyrus did not contain any artistic elements, but was sealed with a seal mentioning "Amenhotep son of Hapu, the royal scribe". He was an architect who lived during the 18th dynasty and was later on deified, together with Imhotep (responsible for building the pyramid of Djoser). Amenhotep (Amenothos) and Imhotep (Asklepios) had their own healer cult in the upper terrace of the temple of Deir el-Bahari during the Ptolemaic and Roman Periods. People came to the temple for incubation and to be healed.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: The rules of the association were presumably rewritten every year. Similar rules of (cult) guilds are known from other associations elsewhere in Egypt (especially from the Fayum).

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text was kept in an archive belonging to the mortuary priest Osoroeris son of Horos. He was an important member of the association. The rest of his archive mainly consisted of documents listing mummies he and his family cared for, as well as contracts in which the rights on mummies were leased, inherited or sold. Such rights basically meant the right to pour the libations for the deceased.

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Rules of a cult guild or association

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The text does not express a formal legal code, but the code of "social" rules to be followed by the members of the association of the mortuary priests. When they did not follow the rules, they had to pay a fine to the temple cash register of Montu. e.g. when they drank more than allowed on so-called "drinking days" (=days on which the members gathered to pour the libations for the deceased as well as to drink themselves in honor of the god Amenophis, Amun of Luxor); e.g. when they insulted the head of the association; e.g. when they left the association

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The papyrus contains a list of "drinking days" on which the mortuary priests poured libations for the deceased in the necropolis. These days also included festivals. The weekly "Decade" Festival (an Egyptian week lasted 10 days) was celebrated according to the civil calendar, while other festivals, such as the Valley Festival, were celebrated according to the Lunar calendar (E.g. on the New Moon during the second month of the summer).

Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: The West is usually seen as the space beyond this world (which is why the tombs are often located on the west bank of the Nile). In addition, the underworld was located underground where the dead were buried.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Although the text itself does not specify any special treatments of the corpses, the mortuary priests (choachytai or water-pourers) were responsible for pouring the libations for the deceased in the necropolis, after they had been mummified by other mortuary priests (taricheutai or lector-priests).

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: This text does not specify any grave goods for burial, but naturally the deceased for which the mortuary priests (choachytai) poured the libations were all buried with specific grave goods.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the libations to be poured by the mortuary priests in or at least near the tombs.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the deceased were considered to be "praised" or "exalted". They presumably received more elaborate offerings from the mortuary priests.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The god Amenope (Amenophis) or Amun of Luxor is mentioned in the text. The association of mortuary priests (choachytai) had dedicated their association to this god. They offered libations in his name on a weekly basis during the Decade Festival

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

Notes: Amenope (Amenophis) or Amun of Luxor had a chthonic aspect.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Oracles for the god Amun could take place during certain festivals.
Whether this knowledge about an individual's future is only related to specific

oracular questions or is related to general knowledge about that individual is unclear

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– Yes

Notes: Thrice a day the daily ritual was performed for the god, in which he was washed, clothed and fed.

↳ Can be hurt?
– I don't know

↳ Can be tricked?
– I don't know

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– I don't know

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: No

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - I don't know

- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god in Thebes during the Ptolemaic Period was Amun. The god had a couple of specific local manifestations. He was Kematef at Medinet Habu, Amenope at Luxor Temple, and Irita at Karnak. However, many of his aspects were merged with the god Osiris (the god of the underworld). This is called the process of Osirianization, which took place during the first millennium BC.

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The god Amenope (Amenophis) or Amun of Luxor travelled every week (every 10 days) from Luxor to Medinet Habu to bring the libations for his ancestors. During this weekly Decade festival, the mortuary priests (choachytai) do the same for the deceased in the necropolis. The procession of Amenope is mentioned in the text. The statue was carried by several individuals, and the head of the association (the lesonis) walked in front of the god.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The mortuary priests were "punished" by fines, when they did not follow the rules stated in the text. But these rules and the fines were enforced by the association and the members themselves and not by a supernatural being. The structure of the rules ensured social cohesion of the group.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The rules of the association of the mortuary priests (choachytai) are very centered on social behavior, including how much they were allowed to drink, not insulting the head of the association, etc.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: Whenever a member of the association dies, two "days of drinking to appease the heart" will be held.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: All the members have to contribute an equal amount of money (in the form of a fee) to the association. Only the head of the association ("the lesonis") and the "second" had to contribute more.

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: All members of the association were members of certain priestly families.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: The rights on mummies (the rights to pour the libations for them) were inherited, leased,

and sold between the members of the association. They all had to cooperate to divide the rights and when disputes arose they were likely first internally solved, before more official instances (e.g. court) were involved.

- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– I don't know
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No

- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No
- ↳ Other important virtues
– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The members of the association were supposed to convene at regular meetings, at least every week (every 10 days).

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: Whenever somebody left the association a fine had to be paid. We can assume leaving the association resulted in social exclusion.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear how many mortuary priests were active at the same time and if all of them participated in the pouring of libations simultaneously. Moreover, also family members of the deceased would have been able to pour libations or bring offerings in addition, thereby also participating in the large-scale ritual.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The libations were poured every 10 days and during specific festivals.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: No animal or human sacrifices are made, but libations were poured and food was offered to the deceased.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– No

Notes: Presumably only food was offered.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– No

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: It was the job of the members of the association to bring the libations and offerings.

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Priestly association

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: These kinds of rules of cult guilds were often made by priestly associations, but also by guilds of other professions (e.g. weavers).

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: Family members of the members of the association were always taken care of.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: Some of the mortuary priests may have received a kind of scribal training in Demotic and/or Greek. At least some members were able to read and write.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text lists the members of the association, which only includes men. However, from other texts in the archives of the mortuary priests, we know also women acted as libation-pourers.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Notes: All members had to contribute a yearly fee. The fee was higher for the head of the association ("the lesonis") and the "second".

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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